

FACTORS OF ECONOMIC GROWTH AND THEORETICAL IDEAS
RELATED TO IT.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6549885>

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Abstract: *Keeping the economic growth of our country in a stable position in this global world and raising our country to a high position among the world countries are becoming the main goal that is in front of our country.*

Keywords: *Economic system, gross domestic product, extensive factor, intensive factor, means of production, socio-economic criteria, economic growth, industrial-agrarian, economic resources.*

Economic growth means an increase in real production and services in the country. Growth is driven by slow growth in one of the components of GDP: consumption, government spending, investment, and net exports. Also, Economic growth brings quantitative growth to the economy.

To guarantee a stable economic growth, there has to be an efficient economic system in every country, in my opinion. For this reason, first of all, I am going to define the term economic system now.

An economic system is a set of principles, rules, and norms enshrined in law that determine the form and content of the basic economic relations that arise in the production, distribution, exchange, and consumption of an economic product. Within the economic system, economic entities and factors of production interact, and these relations are governed by certain rules. The activity of the economic system is organized by a number of means, such as property, money and the monetary system, governmental and non-governmental organizations, enterprises, taxes, income, planning, profits.

Features of the economic system of the Republic of Uzbekistan: simple use of manual labor and natural forces, the availability of extremely inefficient technology, the agrarian nature of production, the mainstay of the economy is extensive agriculture; the existence of industry in the form of handicrafts and domestic industry; economic growth, ie economic autarkism; As the economy grows, products are created mainly for their own consumption, with only the surplus being exchanged. Farms are rarely connected to the market because they are natural consumers money is not important to them because they are self-sufficient; mutual economic relations take place within the economy or within a small local area according to traditional rules and customs; economic activity is based on collective and individual private property; living standards will be low.

In the process of identifying and justifying economic growth, the following should be considered:

- Measuring economic growth;
- Growth factors;
- Economic growth models.

In addition, economic growth depends on several factors:

Quantity and quality of natural resources;

Quantity and quality of labor resources;

The amount of fixed capital;

Technologies;

The second group of factors includes factors that allow to realize the potential for growth in society - demand and distribution factors, that is indirect factors:

- Decrease in the level of market monopolization;
- Tax environment in the economy;
- Efficiency of the credit and banking system;
- Growth of consumption, investment and government spending;
- Growth of exports;
- Opportunities for redistribution of production resources in the economy;
- Formed system of income distribution.

Now, I will turn to economic theories:

In some foreign literature, including Lavrov's Theory and Problems of Economic Growth, the factors of economic growth are classified as follows:

1. Supply factors
2. Distribution factors
3. Consumption factors.

Goods and services are factors of supply, factors of consumption are factors of production that are able to pay. This demand depends on personal income.

In addition, this book contains econometric models of economic growth by Keynesians Roy Harrod (1939) and Evsey Domar (1946). we call them the Harrod-Domar model because there is not much difference between the scientist models. According to this model, the potential of national income to the amount of capital provides economic growth:

$$\underline{Y = \sigma K}$$

Here, Y is the national income, K is the amount of capital used to generate national income, and σ is the capital return ratio. The limitations of the Harrod-Domar model are given in its initial measurements. Leontev's production function used in this model is characterized by the impossibility of interchangeable factors of production - labor and capital, which are incompatible in real life. In addition, all components of this model: income-to-capital ratio, limited propensity to consume, labor force growth, and the development of labor-saving techniques are not interdependent, so the probability of achieving balanced economic growth is zero. For this reason, the Harrod-Domar model is called the "brtiva lesion" model. At the same time, the small imbalance of its components disrupts the balance of the whole system.

Denison calculated the role of each factor in the American economy. If we consider the total growth as 100%, the economic growth achieved due to the increase in labor costs was 32% of the total growth, while the growth rate due to the increase in labor productivity was 68%. A closer look reveals that technical development has led to economic growth of 28 percent, capital expenditures to 19 percent, education and training

to 14 percent, growth to 9 percent, rational allocation of resources to 9 percent, and legislation to 9 percent. can be observed.

Representatives of classical economic growth, including R. Solow (1956), are in the nature of the coefficient of capitalization of labor according to the model of economic growth. They can be written in continuous or non-continuous variants. The capital adequacy ratio represents the value of fixed capital per worker employed in production.

In 1961, the American economist E. Phelps introduced the "golden rule" of savings. According to him, the second sign of optimal balanced growth is that if the growth rate of capital in the equilibrium state corresponds to the growth rate of income, then the growth rate of income is based on the theory of finite productivity. is the ratio between the changes.

Economist Shodiev (2007) gave an econometric definition of economic growth. the most important is to determine which ones and how they differ from the others.

In R. Solow's model, a necessary condition for balanced economic growth is the equality of aggregate demand and aggregate supply. The general proposal in the model is expressed by the production function of Cobba-Douglas, namely:

$$Y = f(L, K, N).$$

In the model, due to the small importance of land in the stage of high technical development, production is assumed to depend only on labor resources and capital:

$$Y = f(L, K).$$

An extended version of this function is:

$$Y = (\Delta Y / \Delta L) L + (\Delta Y / \Delta K) K$$

The model assumes that aggregate demand is determined by investment and consumption costs:

$$Y = S + I.$$

Public spending and net exports are also included in consumption and investment.

Solow sees the volume of output per worker as a function of the level of capitalization.

R. Solow's model reveals the interrelationships of three sources of economic growth - investment, labor force and technical progress. The state can accelerate economic growth by influencing the rate of accumulation and the rate of technical progress.

According to the above diagram, Uzbekistan's gross domestic product advanced 7.4 percent in 2021, following a 1.9 percent expansion in 2020, boosted by agriculture, forestry and fisheries (4.0%); industrial activity (8.7%); construction (6.8%); and the service sector (9.2%).

According to a forecast of economic growth, our countries GDP growth is expected to increase significantly in the coming years. We can see it through the diagram:

Our countries anticipated growth rate in 2022 may grow until 5.8 % (843.2 trillion UZS), according to estimations.

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